

Strategic Impact of Peace Education on Crimes and Criminality Management in Contemporary Nigerian Society

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Abstract

Crimes and criminalities rate are serious threat to peace living and development in a holistic view in Nigeria, today, thus necessitated the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The sample size of the study was one hundred and eighty (180) respondents selected from the civil society. A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted. Data was obtained through self-structured questionnaires by the researchers tagged, "Questionnaire on strategic Impact of Peace Education on Crimes and Criminality Management in Contemporary Nigerian Society", fashioned on four likert rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) rated on 4, 3, 2 and 1 points, respectively. The research instrument were validated by two experts in Test and measurement while, its reliability was determined through test-retest method at two weeks interval. 0.68 coefficient reliability was obtained. Data got were analyzed using, descriptive statistics (simple percentages, frequency counts and mean \bar{X}). Based on the results, conclusions were made that through Peace Education, people's attitude and behaviours could be achieved towards maintaining peace. Also, national orientation towards peace building could also be promoted. Based on conclusions, recommendations were made that; Peace Education should be a compulsory subject or course at every level of education in Nigeria. also, Nigerians should benefits of eschewing behaviour that could truncate peaceful living in the country, Nigeria, and so on.

Keywords: Strategic impact, Peace Education, Crimes, Criminality, Management, Peacefull Living

Background to the Study

Crime and criminality, undoubtedly, are cogs in the wheel of sustainable development in all round perspectives in the contemporary Nigerian Society. Frankly speaking crimes and criminality are trends and challenges that cut across Europe, Asia, Africa, Latin America and other continents with different spate and rate and spate are on a daily increase. Crimes and criminalities are infringements on cooperate existence of the nations' peace-stability, security fundamental human rights, democratic sustainability and consolidation and economic growth and retardation. Akinbi (2015), noted that the victims of these unholy and ungodly acts have no age, religion and ethnic restriction or limitation.

Erinsakin (2014), cardinally identified poverty as a major cause of causative spectrum that make many people to be perpetrating crimes and criminalities. Ilugbamu and Saka-Olokungboye (2021), noted also, that economic deprivation and poverty have planted the seeds of crimes partly, as means of getting money to live a decent standard of life. The high spate of joblessness and widespread decent work deficit also triggered poverty this, leading many Nigerians to take succor in crimes.

In the same spirit and vein, Chuknwuemeka (2022) identified unemployment, corruption, unfair and injustice in allocation and distribution of the nation, Nigeria wealth, weak judiciary system, narcotic indulgency, bad governance, proliferation of light and small arms, among others as factors responsible for crimes prevalence in the country, Nigeria.

The reality today is Nigeria's soil is engulfed with crimes which governments and Nigerians are contending with. The menace if kidnapping, banditry, human rituals, fighting, fraudulent acts, 419 scam, pipe-line vandalization, sex hustling or prostitution, armed robbery, terrorism, communal and ethnic clashes permeating the "hooks and crannies" of the nation, Nigeria.

Abdulkabirs (2017), stated that particularly, the menace of kidnapping has become a general word in both public and private discourse, force and conferences. Dudo (2010) stressed that kidnapping has taken place in form of movement of terrorism, insurgency and banditry in the Northern, Nigeria. However, this does not mean that other regions are not experiencing it but very minimal. The state of kidnapping and insecurity orchestrated by Boko Haram insurgency in the Northern part of the country is quite worrisome, disheartening, alarming ad disturbing

(Akanbi, 2015). Agagu (2007), stressed that pipeline vandalization or oil theft is a popular illegal business in the Niger-Delta area of the nation which Erinsakin (2014) attributed by lack of strategic and appropriate mechanism to address meaningfully environmental challenges caused by the activities of multi-international oil companies, thus, exposing people in the region to untold hardship, poverty, suffering and economic distress. Also, crimes and criminality have been negatively affecting the economic progress and development of the nation. Investments are difficult I nations that are experiencing challenges security.

Human rituals, stealing and armed robbery are caused partly by the desire to improve one's quality of life. In recent times, on a broad day light cases of armed robbery, banks attacked are common unsavory trends. These heneous acts are grave existential threat to polity and cooperate existence of Nigeria. According to Agbelusi (2022),

The issues of insecurity in Nigeria has become something of grave concerned to all well-meaning citizens, most of whom continue to wonder how the country arrived to such a dastardly situation where no one is safe and worse still, rather than abate, the problem is escalating and now totally out of control. Insecurity in Nigeria is a recurring phenomenon that threatens the well-being of its citizens.

In a nutshell, crimes and criminalities are phenomenological and termilological issues of national discourse in Nigeria, today. Several studies had been conducted on crimes ad criminalities and allied issues in Nigeria. However, a paranomic view of most of the studies or researches show that much have not been done on crimes and criminalities vis-à-vis peace education as a strategic impact on how the syndrome could be halted or abated in Nigeria. it was against this backdrop the present study was carried out.

Statement of the Study

Crimes and criminalities prevalence with its antecedence negative effects on national development are issues of national discourse. Crimes take different dimensions, such as; kidnaping, banditry, terrorism, human rituals, armed robbery, stealing, oil theft or pipe-line vandalization, sex hustling or prostitution, "419" scam, and hosts crimes and criminalities are

threat to the nation and several policies and strategies to halt the trends are ineffective, thus, warranted this study on crimes and criminalities management, strategic impact of peace education in contemporary Nigerian society.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was on crimes and criminalities management and strategic impact of peace education in contemporary Nigerian society. The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. ascertain influence of peace education on behavioural reformation towards peace maintenance in Nigeria; and
2. investigate impact of peace education on promotion of national orientation on peace building in Nigeria.

Research Question

Two research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the research.

1. Can peace education impact on behavioural reformation towards peace maintenance in Nigeria?
2. Can peace education promote national orientation on peace building in Nigeria?

Conceptual Framework

Crime / Criminality

The term crime has been variously explained and defined due to different schools of thought. Crime is a legal wrong in which the person who perpetrates it is punished (Isiaka and Okaphor, 2018:1). Tapper (2010), explained crime as an intentional act of violation of criminal law which is committed without defence or excuse and penalized by the state as a felony or misdemeanor. A crime is an intentional or a deliberate act against the land. Crime causes psychological harm, loss of property, breach of societal peace, damage and hosts. Criminality is a state of being a criminal or practicing acts that are considered against the law (Wormith, 2016:1).

Peace Education

Peace education eludes a single definition thus, makes it difficult to conceptualize. According to United Nations Educational and Scientific Organization (2000), “Peace Education is aimed at creating conditions for peace building, resolving conflicts in its different forms by tracing its root, causes and consequences and dealing with ethical, religion and philosophical ethics of human rights”.

In a nation like Nigeria as a country of conglomeration of many ethnics or tribes with different languages and dialects, peace education becomes very vital. Peace education is all about giving or teaching people on the need to maintain an orderly society, eschewed crimes and activities that can truncate socio-peace stability. Peace education objectives can be achieved through the formal and non-formal system of educating and orientating people.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised stakeholders in civil society (community leaders, union leaders, members of charitable organizations, faith based organizations, and hosts). The sample size of the study was one hundred and eighty (180) respondents. A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted. Firstly, the country was stratified into six geo-political regions (North North, North Central, North West, South West, South East and South-South). Then, from each of the six regions, a state with highest population was selected using purposive sampling technique through which a snow-balling sampling technique was used to select thirty (30) respondents to constitute the sample size of the study.

Data was generated for the study through self-structured questionnaire tagged, “Questionnaire on strategic impact of peace education in contemporary Nigeria Society Opinion Survey”. It was fashioned on four likert rating scale: Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD), rated on 4 points; 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The research instruments were validated by two experts in Test and Measurement, while its reliability was determined through test-retest method at two weeks interval. 0.68 coefficient reliability was obtained. Data generated was analyzed using descriptive statistics (simple percentages, frequency counts and mean \bar{X}).

Presentation of Findings and Discussion of Results

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: Can Peace Education Impact on behavioural reformation towards peace maintenance in Nigeria?

Table 1: Showing simple percentages, frequency count and mean (\bar{X}) on can Peace Education Impact on behavioural reformation towards peace maintenance in Nigeria

N = 180, C = 2.5								
S/N	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N	MEAN \bar{X}	Decision
1	PE can change attitudes towards crimes and criminality in Nigeria	156 86.66	19 10.55	3 1.66	2 1.11	180	3.82	Agreed
2	PE is not the best to change people’s attitude towards crimes and criminality in the country	3 1.66	7 3.88	21 11.66	149 82.77	180	1.24	Disagreed
3	Crimes are prevalence because people do not have knowledge of P.E	144 80	19 10.55	16 8.88	1 0.55	180	3.7	Agreed
4	If people have knowledge of P.E, they will eschew involving in crimes	13 7.22	15 8.33	19 10.55	133 73.88	180	1.48	Disagreed
5	PE will enable people to know the negative effects of crimes to the nation	122 67.77	36 20	19 10.55	3 1.66	180	3.53	Agreed
6	Lack of PE knowledge will not have negative consequential effects of crime on the nation peace and tranquility	9 5	11 6.11	19 10.55	141 78.33	180	1.37	Disagreed
	TOTAL WEIGHT	447 41.38	107 9.90	97 8.98	429 39.72		2.52	Agreed

Keys: N = Total Number of Respondents C = Cut of Point, \bar{X} = Mean, SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 above, shows the following responses for item (1); 156 (86.66), 19(10.55), 3(1.66) and 2(11) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Also on item (2), responses got indicated 3(1.66), 7(3.88), 21(11.66) and 149(82.77) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (3), responses got revealed; 144(80), 19(10.55), 16(8.88) and 1(0.55).

On item (4), the following response were obtained; 13(7.22), 15(8.33), 19(10.55) and 133(73.88) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (5), responses got showed; 122(67.77), 36(20), 19(10.55) and 3(1.66) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Finally, on item (6), responses got showed 9(5), 11(6.11), 19(10.55) and 141(78.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Generally speaking, the result shows that the average rate scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.5$) is lesser than the mean of rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.52$), thus, portends that Peace Education could refine people’s behaviour towards maintaining peace in Nigeria.

Research Question Two: Can Peace Education promote national orientation on peace building in Nigeria?

Table 2: Showing simple percentages, frequency count and mean (\bar{X}) on can Peace Education promote national orientation on peace building in Nigeria

N = 180, C = 2.5								
S/N	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N	MEAN \bar{X}	Decision
7	Do you value a nation devoid of crimes and criminality through PE?	139 7.22	36 20	3 1.66	2 1.11	180	3.73	Agreed
8	Even with PE, Nigerians will still not have value for a nation that is freed of crimes and criminalities	3 1.66	9 5	39 21.66	129 71.66	180	1.80	Disagreed
9	P.E will make me to know causes and effects of crimes in human society	147 81.66	11 6.11	16 8.88	6 3.33	180	3.66	Agreed
10	P.E will not make me to know causes and effects of crimes in human society	6 3.33	14 7.77	37 20.55	123 68.33	180	1.46	Disagreed

11	PE will make me to know what constitute as crimes and criminality acts	151 83.88	19 10.55	6 3.33	4 2.22	180	3.76	Agreed
12	PE will not make me to know what constitutes crimes and ctiminality	5 2.77	2 1.11	32 17.77	141 78.33	180	1.28	Disagreed
	TOTAL WEIGHT	451 41.75	91 8.42	133 12.31	405 37.5		2.54	Agreed

Keys: N = Total Number of Respondents C = Cut of Point, \bar{X} = Mean, SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 above, shows the results got on research question two. On item (7), the following responses were obtained; 139 (72.2), 36(20), 3(1.66) and 2(11) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (8), 3(1.66), 9(5), 39(21.66) and 129(71.66) were got for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (9), responses got indicated; 147(81.66), 11(6.11), 16(8.88) and 6(3.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

On item (10), 6(3.33), 14(7.77), 37(20.55) and 123(68.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (11), 151(83.88), 19(10.55), 6(3.33) and 4(2.22) responses were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Finally, on item (12), responses obtained showed 5(2.77), 2(1.11), 32(17.77) and 141(78.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

In a nutshell, the overall result revealed that the average rate scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.5$) is lesser than the mean of rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.54$). Hence, shows that Peace Education could enhance or promote national orientation towards peace in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Based on the results, conclusions were made that Peace Education could modify and result to behavioural changes towards maintaining peace in Nigeria. In the same vein, Peace Education could also results to national orientation towards peace building in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Premise on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Peace Education should be a compulsory subject on course at every level of education in Nigeria.
2. There should be a national orientation on the relevance of Peace Education on crimes and criminalities control in Nigeria.
3. Seminars, conferences and forum should be organize in respect of Peace Education in the country, Nigeria.
4. Nigerians should be well sensitized on the benefits of eschewing behaviours that can truncate peaceful living in the country.
5. There should be a non-formal approach to orientate Nigerians on Peace Education and host of others

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